

Experiences and Implementation of Patient-initiated follow-up implementation for chronic conditions: A qualitative evidence synthesis protocol.

Authors: Elodie Besnier¹, Binyam Bogale¹, Mads Solberg¹, Ralf Kirchhoff¹, Jannike Dyb Oksavik¹, Monica Marchant², Simon Lewin^{1,3 4}

Affiliations

¹ Department of Health Sciences in Ålesund, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Ålesund, Norway

² Section for Teaching and Learning Support, Subject Specialist for Medicine and Health Sciences, NTNU University Library in Ålesund, Norwegian university of science and technology, Ålesund Norway

³ Health Systems Research Unit, South African Medical Research Council, Cape Town, South Africa

⁴ Centre for Epidemic Interventions Research, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway

Abstract

Background

The burden of chronic conditions has been growing worldwide. These conditions put an enormous pressure on health systems, communities and patients due to the daily management and close follow-up they require. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic severely disrupted routine care for people with chronic conditions, creating and expanding a need to explore new digital or hybrid care models with very little time and preparation. Patient-initiated follow up (PIFU) is an increasingly popular model for providing healthcare, especially for patients whose condition require follow-up over a prolonged period. PIFU holds the promise of more efficient health services and patient empowerment, including in the context of health emergencies. While this complex intervention has grown in popularity for chronic disease management, there is considerable variation in its implementation across health conditions, care settings, and patient groups. These differences and their implications for the design and delivery of PIFU approaches are poorly understood. Existing literature found mixed results in the experience of patients under PIFU approaches while the views and experiences of health professionals and other stakeholders have been comparatively less explored. As PIFU approaches are being adopted more widely, it is essential to better understand how stakeholders view, experience and deliver these

approaches in order to better understand the factors affecting PIFU's implementation, including as an approach for sustaining routine care during health emergencies.

This qualitative evidence synthesis links to a systematic review assessing the effects of patient-initiated follow-up for diabetes care (PROSPERO registration number 1331488) (Bogale et al., 2026).

Objectives

(1) To inform the design, delivery and use of future PIFU approaches for chronic conditions by exploring the views, experiences and practices of patients enrolled in PIFU, their relatives, and healthcare workers, managers and other professionals involved in providing PIFU services for people with chronic conditions. (2) To explore differences between PIFU under normal circumstances and PIFU in times of health emergencies.

Search methods

We will search the electronic databases MEDLINE, CINAHL Complete, EMBASE, Web of Science, AJOL and ProQuest Dissertations and Theses for studies published since 1995. We will conduct a grey literature search in Google. We will conduct a cited reference search for all included studies in Paperfetcher.

Selection criteria

We will include primary qualitative studies on stakeholders' views, experiences and practices regarding PIFU approaches for chronic conditions (apart from cancer). Stakeholders include adult patients living with one or more chronic conditions managed through a PIFU approach, their relatives, healthcare workers and managers involved in PIFU services, and other support staff involved in these services. We will include studies from any country and in any settings where PIFU is received or delivered. We will not exclude studies on the basis of language.

Data collection and analysis

We will use a framework analysis approach for data extraction and synthesis using NVivo15. We will assess methodological limitations using CASP, unless the beta version of CAMELOT in iSoQ becomes available before our extraction begins. We will use the GRADE-CERQual (Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative research) approach in iSoQ to assess our confidence in each finding. We will examine each review finding to identify factors that may influence intervention implementation and developed implications for practice and for emergency preparedness.

Background

Description of the topic

The burden of chronic conditions, defined as “health problems that require ongoing management over a period of years or decades” (World Health Organization, 2002, p. 11), has been growing worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 43 million people died from these diseases in 2021. Over 80% of these deaths occurred in low- and middle-income countries (WHO, 2025b). By their duration and chronicity, these conditions put an enormous pressure on health systems but also communities by the daily management and close follow-up they require.

Patient-initiated follow up (PIFU) is an increasingly popular model for providing healthcare, especially for patient whose condition require a follow-up over a prolonged period. Under a PIFU approach, eligible patients initiate follow-up appointments based on their needs or symptoms rather than on a schedule set by the health system. While the design and delivery of PIFU approaches vary across settings and health conditions (Sherlaw-Johnson et al., 2024a), a core component of PIFU is that contacts with a healthcare professional (HCP) regarding the management of a chronic condition are triggered by the patient themselves rather than scheduled at set intervals.

Reed & Crellin (2022) identifies seven dimensions to consider in the design of PIFU care pathways:

- Patient selection and assessment to initiate PIFU (versus fixed follow-up)
- Patient induction and education to support self-management and inform about PIFU
- Patient (self-)monitoring
- Contact and communication with healthcare services
- Escalation and triage of patient requests for follow-up
- Safety nets
- Discharge and review of whether a patient should remain under the PIFU approach

PIFU aims to improve health system responsiveness, efficiency and increase patient autonomy (Paterson et al., 2025; Reed & Crellin, 2022; Whear et al., 2020). While this complex intervention has grown in popularity for chronic disease management, there is considerable variation in its implementation across health conditions, care settings, patient groups (Paterson et al., 2025; Reed & Crellin, 2022). These differences and their implications for the design and delivery of PIFU approaches are poorly understood. Existing literature found mixed results in the experience of patients under PIFU approaches, while the views and experiences of health professionals and other stakeholders have been comparatively less explored in the literature (Dretzke et al., 2023; Paterson et al., 2025; Reed & Crellin, 2022). As PIFU approaches are being adopted more widely, it is essential to better understand how stakeholders view, experience and deliver these in order to better understand the factors affecting PIFU’s implementation. Variations across contexts and

patient groups are also essential to understand the transferability of different features in the PIFU approaches across settings, conditions and/or patient groups as well as PIFU's implication for health equity. A qualitative evidence synthesis is a tool well-suited to explore these issues by consolidating current qualitative research on PIFUs in order to understand variations in stakeholder experiences across different contexts and factors affecting the implementation of these approaches.

This review links to a systematic review assessing the effects of patient-initiated follow-up for diabetes care (PROSPERO registration number 1331488) (Bogale et al., 2026).

How the intervention might work / How the health condition might affect people

By realigning access to healthcare with patient needs, PIFU aims to support patients' autonomy and empower patients to engage with their healthcare (Kershaw et al., 2022; Paterson et al., 2025). As follow-ups are only scheduled when needed, PIFU may also reduce the treatment burden patients living with chronic conditions face due to healthcare, including costs of healthcare and travel time dedicated to fixed follow up, stress caused by healthcare visits (Paterson et al., 2025). However, the requirements of self-management central to PIFU approaches may also shift the responsibility of care away from the health system and onto patients and their relatives. Thus, it may create new administrative, financial and emotional burdens while fuelling inequities between patients (e.g. patients using a minority language, patients with low health literacy, patients with fewer resources and support) (Dretzke et al., 2023; Paterson et al., 2025). As many PIFU approaches also involve using digital tools for self-management or to contact healthcare professionals (HCPs), access and use of such tools may further shape stakeholders' experience under PIFU or create new disparities between different population groups. A landscape analysis of digital tools use for routine care during COVID-19 carried out in the RAPIDE project (Horizon Europe RAPIDE project, 2026) highlighted that older adults, people with low digital literacy, those with limited access to smartphones or broadband, and patients with physical, cognitive, or language difficulties often struggle to navigate digital systems independently or to interpret health information. Individuals in rural or low-income settings may also experience reduced access. These groups may therefore find PIFU difficult, unsafe, or anxiety-provoking, potentially widening existing inequalities. Some groups may be willing to try PIFU but may need extensive training and support before they can be enrolled while others may need training and information in their native language. Understanding how different PIFU features are experienced by people living with chronic conditions and their relatives is important to inform the design, delivery and institutionalization of this approach as well as its consequences in terms of patient empowerment.

For the healthcare system, PIFU is designed to make healthcare more efficient by reducing both missed appointments and unnecessary consultations, thus reducing waste and allowing the reallocation of healthcare resources to other tasks. PIFU approaches are also supposed to ensure a timely access to healthcare when patients *do* need it, thus avoiding delays in care that may lead to complication or the diagnosis of secondary conditions (Kershaw et al.,

2022; Reed & Crellin, 2022; Sherlaw-Johnson et al., 2024a). Finally, as a planned, on-demand system, PIFU approaches can also facilitate task shifting across levels of care (e.g., from specialist care to primary care) and across healthcare worker cadres (e.g., from general practitioners to primary care nurses), depending on the needs of patients and the availability of human resources. This task-shifting is guided by a planned triage system that directs patients to an appropriate healthcare service level depending on their health issues. However, some of these effects have been debated in the literature, with concerns over the additional burden and workload PIFU can potentially create for health services as well as concerns with certain patients delaying seeking care (Dretzke et al., 2023; Sherlaw-Johnson et al., 2024a). Patient selection and the suitability of PIFU to different population groups (even within the same condition) has also been identified as a concern among HCPs (Chainrai et al., 2024; Dretzke et al., 2023). Understanding how HCP and other staff involved in PIFU management experience and view this approach may help identify problematic or successful features in PIFU's design and delivery as well as its consequences for the health workforce and system.

Why is it important to do this review?

PIFU approaches are being adopted more widely, especially since the COVID-19 pandemic where routine care was disrupted by the need for acute response to the pandemic (Paterson et al., 2025; Reed & Crellin, 2022). For example, the National Health Service in England is encouraging the adoption of PIFU to meet the national goal of reducing outpatient follow-ups by 25% between 2019 and 2024 (Sherlaw-Johnson et al., 2024a). In Calgary, Canada, PIFU is being developed for rheumatology to address both a growing number of patients needing rheumatology care and growing waiting times for specialist care (Ester et al., 2025a). When defining the topic and scope of this QES and the associated effect review, and as part of the RAPIDE project (Horizon Europe RAPIDE project, 2026), we carried out online consultation meetings with three Norwegian health Trust on November 25th and December 2nd, 2025 to identify priority topics with a digital health element and that can help with sustaining routine care during health emergencies. These consultations identified PIFU as an intervention of interest, as PIFU should allow freeing up healthcare resources while ensuring continuity of care for people with chronic conditions. PIFU also allows integrating digital health technology for remote monitoring and e-consultation. Therefore, it has been identified as a relevant solution to scale up in times of emergencies. While this approach is broadly adopted for chronic condition care in Norway, Health Trusts also highlighted a number of concerns regarding the use and delivery of PIFU, its implication for patient care, and the use of digital tools in this approach.

The role and involvement of patients are central to PIFU approaches, as they are expected to initiate the follow-up and monitor their condition autonomously. Their experience and preferences are essential to the design and successful delivery of PIFU (Dretzke et al., 2023; Paterson et al., 2025). With chronic conditions, the duration of disease and its implications on several aspect of daily life (e.g. regular monitoring, nutrition, activities) also make the support and involvement of relatives in the management of the condition important aspects of to consider when developing new care pathways. From the health system's perspective,

as PIFU is presented as a way to make the healthcare more efficient and reduce the burden on the health system, the views and experience of HCPs and health managers are central to explore the reality of these goals, as well as the factors and that may facilitate or hinder the introduction, scale up and institutionalization of PIFU approaches. However, the experience of these stakeholders have been comparatively less explored in the literature (Dretzke et al., 2023; Reed & Crellin, 2022; Sherlaw-Johnson et al., 2024a).

PIFU in the context of public health emergencies

During the COVID-19 pandemic, routine follow-up care for many people living with chronic conditions in many countries was heavily disrupted to reduce pressure on hospital services and limit the risk of infection in these vulnerable populations. Additionally, many primary care services closed or moved to online consultation, to minimize person-to-person contact. Support to people living with chronic conditions on how they were supposed to continue manage their care under these circumstances varied greatly. Some people were instructed to contact health services if their condition worsened, while others received little information about how or where their follow-up care would continue. These emergency-driven disruptions to routine services effectively created an unplanned form of patient-led care, as the responsibility for deciding when to seek further care was largely shifted to people living with chronic conditions and their caregivers.

Because of its structured, patient-centred nature, PIFU offers a particularly valuable window for understanding hybrid care dynamics in the context of public health emergencies. By reducing the burden of unnecessary routine appointments, PIFU approaches can help health systems to preserve scarce capacity when emergencies generate sudden surges in demand – a key organizational challenge identified during the COVID-19 pandemic. As PIFU approaches can facilitate task shifting, they allow flexibility between levels of care and the availability of human resources during an emergency.

PIFU also aligns with emergency response priorities by supporting hybrid care delivery. Patients gain direct access to a service point (often digital) through which they can request follow-up, while also being empowered through information, training, and awareness of red-flag symptoms. This more patient-centred approach is intended to support safe triage during health crises when face-to-face consultations may be limited. PIFU can also incorporate digital remote monitoring or electronic patient-reported outcomes as a safety net, providing data that helps clinicians focus attention on the patients who most require follow-up most urgently. This follow up may, in turn, be provided using telemedicine modalities.

PIFU can therefore help manage several of the key challenges for scaling up digital health tools in health emergencies: access to technology (such as devices to transmit health data remotely), triage protocols, health and digital health literacy, and data-management capacity. PIFU can be implemented using analogue systems initially and expanded digitally as capacity allows. The approach also has the potential to reduce the volume of remote-monitoring data that must be managed by clinicians by shifting timely self-monitoring to patients.

Finally, PIFU may support continuity of care for people with chronic conditions, who often face heightened vulnerability during health emergencies. The model promotes patient autonomy, maintains access to follow-up when needed, and integrates hybrid elements that can be sustained even during prolonged disruptions. For these reasons, PIFU has potential as an adaptable, scalable approach for strengthening chronic-care pathways in future public-health emergencies. In this QES, we will examine how health emergencies may affect the delivery and use of PIFU for chronic conditions and the implications of this for implementation during such emergencies.

For some groups of people living with chronic conditions, the PIFU approach may not be suitable. As previously described, some groups struggle to navigate digital systems independently or to interpret health information while others may experience barriers to accessing digital technologies. We also described how certain groups require extensive support to initiate or sustain autonomous management of their condition under PIFU, which might not be feasible under a health emergency, where resources are stretched. PIFU should therefore be considered one of a palette of hybrid care interventions that could be used to sustain routine healthcare during a health emergency. In this review, we will explore the equity implications of implementing a PIFU approach and strategies that might be useful in addressing or mitigating inequities.

How this review might inform or supplement what is already known in this area

The majority of reviews on PIFU have focused on the effectiveness, safety and healthcare utilization through the analysis of quantitative studies (e.g. trials, cohort studies - see (Kershaw et al., 2022; Reed & Crellin, 2022; Whear et al., 2020)). While essential to inform healthcare decisions, these reviews do not provide an understanding of the lived experience and challenges faced by stakeholders involved in PIFU services. This information is key to inform the adequate design and delivery of PIFU approaches, as well as for understanding the consequences this approach has for stakeholders.

During our initial scoping, we identified two recent qualitative evidence syntheses (QES) on PIFU, which were both exclusively focused on cancer care (Dretzke et al., 2023; Paterson et al., 2025). Another review extracted findings from selected qualitative studies but did not analyse or synthesize them. This review also highlighted the small number of specialties covered in the included studies as an important gap in the literature (Reed & Crellin, 2022). This current review aims to address these gaps by including a wide range of chronic conditions outside of cancer.

The QES by Dretzke et al. (2023) and Paterson et al. (2025) included cancer patients, their families and HCPs. The views of support staff and managers were not explored. The qualitative data extraction from Reed and Crellin (2022) did include two studies exploring the organizational context of PIFU but did not provide the views and experiences of the actors involved in this aspect of PIFU services. In our QES, we aim to include the views,

experiences and practices of all the stakeholders involved in PIFU to inform future PIFU interventions holistically.

Additionally, the studies included in these three reviews came primarily from the UK and to a lesser extent, Scandinavia. The lack of geographical and cultural diversity of the included studies was identified as a limitation by both QES. By searching databases targeting the Global South, we hope to help fill this gap in the literature.

Finally, while all three reviews highlighted how the COVID-19 pandemic had affected health services and/or accelerated the adoption of PIFU, only one QES included one study focused on stakeholders' experience of PIFU during this health emergency (Paterson et al., 2025).

Objectives

To inform the design, delivery and use of future PIFU approaches for chronic conditions by exploring the views, experiences and practices of patients enrolled in PIFU, their relatives, and healthcare workers, managers and other professionals involved in providing PIFU services for people with chronic conditions. As the RAPIDE project focuses on emergency preparedness and continuity of care, we will also explore differences between PIFU under normal circumstances and PIFU in times of emergencies (if the data allows it).

Research questions

1. What do stakeholders consider as factors affecting the delivery, patient experience and consequences of PIFU approaches for chronic conditions (e.g. context, PIFU's characteristics)?
2. What are the views, experiences and practices of the healthcare workers, managers and other professionals delivering PIFU services?
3. What are the views, experiences, and practices of people living with chronic conditions enrolled in PIFU services and of their relatives?
4. What can the views, experiences, and practices of stakeholders indicate about the consequences of the PIFU approaches in shifting responsibility, access, workload and risks across stakeholder groups, particularly, among groups that may experience inequities?
5. How do health emergencies affect the delivery and use of PIFU for chronic conditions?

Methods

When preparing this protocol/review, we used the Cochrane Protocol and Review Template for Qualitative Evidence Synthesis (Glenton et al., 2023).

Stakeholder engagement

Following the Cochrane training “Involving people” guidance (Pollock et al., n.d.) and the TRANSFER approach (H. Munthe-Kaas et al., 2020), we will engage with stakeholders at several stages of our review.

Topic Scoping

As previously described, when defining the topic and scope of this QES and the associated effect review, we carried out online consultation meetings with three Norwegian health Trusts to identify priority topics.

Method definition and protocol design

We will organize consultation with people living with chronic conditions and healthcare professionals involved in PIFU services for chronic conditions care. These stakeholders were identified through collaborators involved in the RAPIDE project and through posts published on the Healthcare Information For All (HIFA) forum. Feedback from these stakeholders will be collected during online meetings and/or via email correspondence. The consultations with people living with diabetes and professionals in this field will be carried out together with the effect review team.

Prior to these consultations, we developed a set of common questions around four topics, to guide the discussions:

- Important outcomes for assessing the effects of patient-initiated follow up (PIFU) programs for people with diabetes (used for the effect review)
- Factors affecting the transferability of study findings from one setting to another
- Concerns over health inequities and PIFU
 - o Factors of inequities due to the chronic condition (higher risks, higher prevalence, higher complication rate)
 - o Factors of inequities due to the type of stakeholder
 - o Inequities due to the design and implementation of PIFU services (elements in the intervention that lead to certain groups facing inequities)
- Struggles implementing (for practitioners) or following (for patients) the PIFU approach

The notes from these consultations will be summarized around each of these questions and will be used to inform several elements of our method, including our analytical framework, identifying relevant factors of inequities to consider in our analysis, and our confidence assessment on the review’s findings.

Developing implications for practice

We will send our prompts for future implementers, developed based on our review’s findings, to a selection of stakeholders working with different chronic conditions to gather their feedback about the relevance of these prompts to practice and the manner in which they are phrased and presented.

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of studies

We will include primary studies that use qualitative study designs such as ethnography, phenomenology, case studies, grounded theory studies and qualitative process evaluations. We will include studies that use both qualitative methods for data collection (e.g., focus group discussions, individual interviews, observation, diaries, document analysis, open-ended survey questions) and qualitative methods for data analysis (e.g. thematic analysis, framework analysis, grounded theory).

We will exclude studies that collect data using qualitative methods but do not analyse these data using qualitative analysis methods (e.g., open-ended survey questions where the response data are analysed using descriptive statistics only). We will also exclude mixed methods studies, as it may be challenging to extract elements relating on qualitative data from synthesized findings in such studies.

We will include both published and unpublished studies and studies published in any language (See also section on Language translation below).

We will include studies regardless of whether or not they were conducted alongside studies of the effect of PIFU as covered in a companion effect review (Bogale et al., 2026).

We will not exclude studies based on our assessment of methodological limitations. We will use this information about methodological limitations to assess our confidence in the review findings.

Topic of interest

Phenomenon of interest

We will focus on studies of stakeholders' views, experiences and practices regarding PIFU approaches for chronic conditions. We will include PIFU for chronic conditions at any stage of implementation and use (e.g., pilot, scale-up, PIFU as standard care, institutionalized approaches).

For this QES, we define the core components of PIFU as follows, adapted from the Reed and Crellin(2022) definition:

Patient contact, communication with healthcare services

Follow-up (FU)¹ is triggered 'on-demand' by people living with chronic conditions according to their individual needs and symptoms. People living with chronic conditions' needs and symptoms may be collected by the health system using either digital remote monitoring or analogue approaches (e.g., on paper and then shared by phone) and may use standardized PROMs (i.e., patient-initiated appointments may be supported by technology)

- FU may be digital, in-person or both and may be either synchronous or asynchronous

¹ We define a 'follow-up' as any contact or appointment between a patient and a healthcare provider that is intended to follow up issues related to the patient's health condition. This includes online telephone and face-to-face appointments with any kind of healthcare provider.

- People living with chronic conditions under PIFU have a direct / pre-planned access mechanism, channel or pathway to a service point where the FU arrangement is made when needed (e.g., via telephone, digital portal) (Balhorn et al., 2022; Hardy, 2024; Sherlaw-Johnson et al., 2024b). Information on this mechanism may be provided to patients through any channels (e.g. on paper, online).

Patient induction and education about PIFU and self-monitoring:

People living with chronic conditions are informed about their responsibilities to seek FU and how to do so when necessary. They receive information or training from the health system about signs and symptoms related to their health condition, including ‘red flags’ that would require a FU (Leitch et al., 2025). This may include support tools (e.g. apps, booklets), and decision aids to support self-monitoring and timely follow-up (Ester et al., 2025b; Paterson et al., 2025).

PIFU interventions may also include the following elements, although we will not exclude studies on this base:

Patient selection and assessment to initiate PIFU (versus scheduled follow-up):

- Health services define specific eligibility criteria for a patient to be offered or placed under a PIFU care pathways, such as stable disease activity, low-risk conditions, or absence of complex comorbidities (Ester et al., 2025b; Sherlaw-Johnson et al., 2024b; Subdar et al., 2024)

Response of the health services:

Routine FU appointments are scheduled at a lower frequency by the health services (compared to care pathways outside of PIFU) or not scheduled at all by the health services.

Safety nets and Review of whether a patient should remain under the PIFU approach:

- Health services for chronic conditions establish standard operating procedures to track patients within the PIFU service or reach out to defaulting patients etc. For example, they may initiate FU
 - after a period without contact with a patient (e.g., after 6 months without contact)
 - based on remotely monitoring data provided by the patient (e.g., PROMS, remotely monitored physiological data), which signal abnormal changes in their condition
- Health services have safety net guidelines and protocols informing what to do if a patient’s condition changes, allowing patients to be reviewed, escalated, returned to scheduled FU, or discharged as needed to avoid harm. (Ester et al., 2025b; Reed & Nadia, n.d.; Sengupta et al., 2024; Sherlaw-Johnson et al., 2024b).

We will exclude models of care where need-based follow-up is initiated without patient involvement (e.g. exclusively based on PROMS automatically sent to the HCP). We will also exclude studies on focused on services that are not directly part of PIFU but are provided to

people because of their chronic conditions (e.g. support at home for activities of daily living, care for other conditions that are not managed through a PIFU approach).

We define chronic conditions as “health problems that require ongoing management over a period of years or decades” (World Health Organization, 2002, p. 11). These include for instance diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, lung diseases, rheumatological conditions, dermatological, neurological, renal or mental health conditions. We will include studies of any chronic condition apart from cancer care, where there are existing syntheses (Dretzke et al., 2023; Paterson et al., 2025)). We will exclude PIFU for surgery unrelated to chronic conditions (e.g. PIFU for common fractures). As PIFU requires people living chronic conditions to be able to understand their condition and make decisions for their care autonomously to the requirement of the PIFU approach, we will also exclude chronic conditions affecting people’s cognitive functions (e.g. dementia, severe schizophrenia). Finally, we will exclude patient-initiated acute care requests (e.g. request for emergency or crisis intervention at home) as these do not qualify as PIFU under our definition.

Participants

We will include studies involving:

- People living with one or more chronic conditions, and who are over 18 years of age, receiving care for these conditions through a PIFU approach
- Relatives and family members of the person with a chronic condition enrolled in PIFU services
- Healthcare workers providing care to people living with a chronic condition that is managed through PIFU services
- Healthcare managers responsible for PIFU services
- Other professionals working in healthcare services and involved in PIFU services (e.g., administrative support staff, IT support staff)

We will exclude studies involving children and adolescents under 18 years old receiving PIFU services for a chronic condition, as PIFU approaches for that population are different from those implemented in adult population because these interventions have to be mediated by a caregiver or legal guardian.

Settings

We will include studies from any country and any setting in which PIFU services are delivered or received (home, community, primary care, secondary or other levels of care).

For the research question on health emergencies, we define “health emergencies” as serious events (e.g. severe epidemic) that pose a serious threat to population health, thus having a

high impact on the health system and requiring immediate action. We define “normal circumstances” as time when the health system is not facing an emergency.

Search methods for identification of studies

Electronic searches

An information specialist (MM) will develop the search strategies in consultation with the review authors (BB, EB, SL, MS). The search terms for PIFU-related terms will be developed jointly for both this synthesis and the effect review, and reviewed by a second information specialist for validation. We will use search filter for qualitative studies provided by MEDLINE (Canada’s Drug Agency, 2026; Wagner et al., 2020) and translate it into other databases. We will apply the age filter in each database to search for studies in adults. Finally, as the oldest study found by previous reviews on PIFU was published in 1996 (Lahdensuo 1996 in (Whear et al., 2020)), we will limit our search to studies published since 1995.

We will search the following electronic databases:

- MEDLINE (EbscoHost)
- CINAHL Complete (EbscoHost)
- EMBASE (Elsevier)
- Web of Science (Clarivate)
- AJOL (African Journals Online)
- ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global

We had initially planned to search the Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) to better captured the literature from Latin America and ran initial searches in this database, finding no results. Since Web of Science includes both SciELO and the Virtual Health Library (VHL) (Biblioteca Virtual en Salud, BVS), and allow more advanced search strategies, we chose to replace SciELO with Web of Science in our search.

We will develop search strategies for each database. We will not apply any limits on language or publication date. We will search all databases from inception to the date of search. We will include a methodological filter for qualitative studies. See Appendix 1 for the EMBASE search strategy, which we will adapt for other databases. We will provide appendices for all strategies used.

Grey literature

To identify relevant grey literature, we will search Google using search terms around “PIFU”, “chronic conditions” and “qualitative research”. For each variation of the search terms, we will screen the results displayed on the first five pages on the platform.

Searching other resources

We will review the reference lists of all the included studies and key references (i.e. relevant systematic reviews). We will conduct a cited reference search for all included studies in Paperfletcher (Pallath & Zhang, 2023). We will also search for any relevant qualitative sibling studies to trials including in the parallel effects review (e.g., qualitative process evaluations).

Selection of studies

Review authors (EB, BB, SL, MS, JDO, RK) will independently assess the titles and abstracts of the identified records in duplicate to evaluate eligibility in EPPI-Reviewer.

We will retrieve the full text of all the papers identified as potentially relevant by two review authors. Two review authors will then assess these papers independently. We will resolve disagreements by consensus or, when required, by involving a third review author.

We will include a table listing studies that we excluded from our review at full text stage and the main reasons for exclusion.

Where the same study, using the same sample and methods, has been presented in different reports, we will collate these reports so that each study (rather than each report) is the unit of interest in our review. We will include a PRISMA flow diagram to show our search results and the process of screening and selecting studies for inclusion.

Machine Learning

To maximize efficiency, we will use EPPI-Reviewer's machine learning function to carry out priority screening. This function is based on a ranking algorithm that brings forward the most relevant studies by continuously learning from the reviewers' decisions. At the title and abstract screening, stage, we will screen until the priority screening graph plateaus and no new included records are identified for 500 records (Glenton et al., 2024; Page et al., 2021).

Language translation

For titles and abstracts that are published in a language that none of the review team are proficient in (i.e. languages other than English, Scandinavian languages, French, German or Spanish), we will carry out an initial translation with AI (Copilot). If this translation indicates inclusion, or if the translation is inadequate to make a decision, we will retrieve the full text of the paper. We will carry out translation of the full text in two different AI tools (ChatGPT; Copilot). If significant differences in translation are noted between the two tools, we will then ask native speakers or members of our network networks proficient in that language to assist us in assessing the full text of the paper for inclusion. If this cannot be done for a paper in a particular language, the paper will be listed as 'studies awaiting classification', to ensure transparency in the review process.

Sampling of studies

Qualitative evidence synthesis aims for variation in concepts rather than an exhaustive sample, and large amounts of study data can impair the quality of the analysis. Once we have identified all studies that are eligible for inclusion, we will assess whether the number

or data richness is likely to represent a problem for the analysis and will consider selecting a sample of studies.

If the number of eligible studies is considered so large that it may threaten the quality of the synthesis, we will apply a purposive maximum variation sampling frame to select the studies to include in the synthesis (Ames et al., 2024). As our phenomenon of interest (PIFU) can lead to variations and that previous QES on PIFU in cancer have identified variations in experience across different patient groups, our sampling approach must allow us to capture this diversity. The dimensions of variation we will use to prioritise and sample studies will be:

- 1) Studies that provide data on less commonly studied stakeholders (e.g. managers and support staff, relatives of the people under PIFU), or settings (e.g. low- and middle-income countries)
- 2) Studies that provide data on population groups at risk of inequities in the context of a PIFU approach
- 3) Studies with rich data

For this last dimension, we will use the contextual thickness/conceptual richness tool developed by Ames and colleagues (Ames et al., 2024).

Data extraction

Three authors (MS, JDO, RK) will extract descriptive information about included studies and publication into iSoQ. These will include:

- Characteristics of the record: authors, title, year
- Characteristics of the study: participants (including sub-groups – see below, “subgroup analysis” for the list of subgroups), country, setting, whether the study took place during a health emergency, objective and method
- Descriptive characteristics of the PIFU service according to the categories identified in our definition of PIFU (based on the seven dimensions developed by Reed and Crellin (2022), as well as the duration, and stage of implementation/institutionalization.

Assessing the methodological limitations of included studies

Review authors [MS, JDO, RK] will independently assess methodological limitations in duplicate for each study using the CASP tool (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, 2022). As we are aware that a new tool to assess methodological limitations (CAMELOT, (H. M. Munthe-Kaas et al., 2024)) is currently being finalized and integrated in the confidence assessment software iSoQ, we will consider moving to this tool should that integration be finalized and made available before we finish screening. Where any of the review authors are also authors of included studies, they will not be involved in the assessment of the study’s methodological limitations. We will resolve disagreements by consensus or, when required, by involving a third review author. We will assess methodological limitations according to the following domains

We will report our assessments in iSoQ and narratively in the manuscript describing our results.

Data management, analysis and synthesis

Analytical approach

We will apply the ‘best fit framework synthesis (BFFS)’ approach to extract, analyse and synthesise the evidence (Brunton et al., 2024). This approach allows using existing relevant frameworks and theories to analyse included studies while leaving the possibility of further inductive coding using thematic analysis to reflect findings the preexisting framework cannot accommodate. By working from existing theoretical constructs, BFFS is also particularly adapted to synthesis developed under strict time constraints (Booth & Carroll, 2015). As our objective is to inform the design, delivery and use of PIFU services for chronic conditions while being sensitive to potential disparities between context or populations, we reviewed implementation research frameworks and assessed which one(s) would accommodate strong diversity and a strong focus on health equity. We chose the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) as our starting point. This “meta-theoretical” framework was developed as a synthesis of existing implementation theories and provides a unified taxonomy for implementation sciences while allowing flexibility to select constructs relevant to the context(s) or purpose of the study (e.g. aspect of the implementation explored)(Damschroder et al., 2009). Following the BFFS approach, we reviewed the CFIR’s five domains and 39 constructs and deconstituted those relevant to our QES into a four-stage implementation chain that will serve as our analytical framework (Table 1). We will also use the information collected through stakeholder engagement to refine our selection and definitions of relevant codes.

The first stage (the PIFU environment) draws on intervention characteristics, inner setting, and outer setting to examine the factors shaping how PIFU is designed and structured, including its perceived advantage over alternative approaches, its complexity in practice, and the organizational readiness for this approach . The second stage (the delivery) focuses on the characteristics of individuals and the delivery process to explore the mindset, confidence, and practices of healthcare workers as they provide care under the PIFU model. The third stage (the experience) returns to individual characteristics and outer setting, now from the perspective of people living with chronic conditions and their relatives, asking how well the PIFU model fits their home context and whether they trust and feel capable of managing their own care. These three stages together feed into a fourth (the consequence) which synthesizes findings across domains to examine shifts in responsibility, access, workload and risks across stakeholders, gaps in access, and the redistribution of risk, particularly for groups that may experience inequities. This sequencing ensures that conclusions about equity and accountability emerge as logical outcomes of the full implementation chain rather than isolated observations and directly maps onto the four research questions guiding this QES.

Table 1 illustrates the full mapping of CFIR constructs onto each stage, including constructs excluded and the rationale for their exclusion. For each stage, the analytical framework is

further operationalized into a set of coder questions (fifth column). These are plain-language prompts that guide reviewers in identifying and coding relevant data from included studies against each included CFIR construct. Instead of asking coders to work directly from abstract CFIR construct definitions (which may generate expanding, overlapping codes), they will work from a small set of concrete, plain-language questions throughout the analysis (around three per stage, compressing the framework into twelve focal prompts).

Where data from included studies does not map onto the predefined framework, but relevant, coders will generate inductive codes, in keeping with the BFFS approach. Codes flagged as distinct from the CFIR-derived categories will be kept in a separate folder and assessed in regular discussions between the two coders to ensure consistency. We consider such codes as likely to emerge in response to our forth research question, as some these shifts and changes are not well covered in the CFIR. Inductive codes from each coder will be examined alongside the framework-derived ones before merging, and either absorbed into an existing CFIR-construct where appropriate or representing a new common theme outside the framework. If relevant, new suggested codes or themes will also be shared and discussed with the wider review teams during bi-monthly meetings.

Two review authors [EB, SL/BB] will code included studies independently using NVivo 15. We will pilot the coding framework by selecting two of the included studies that most closely match our review objectives and should therefore include relevant data. Each coder will code these two studies independently and then meet to compare their application of codes, discuss discrepancies and, where needed, refine code explanations. This calibration process will help to build a shared understanding of the coding framework and coding process. After this, the two coders will split the remaining included studies between them and independently code these, meeting as needed to discuss any queries that arise. After coding five studies each, the coders will review each other's coding on one of the studies coded separately to ensure that the framework continues to be applied coherently and review inductively-created codes. This process will be repeated until all the studies have been coded. Once all the data has been extracted and coded, the coders will first review and compare their inductive codes against the framework and harmonize or merge their terminology and use. Then, the two coders will merge the two sets of codes, group the data that have the same or similar codes and then synthesise these to create draft review findings. Codes from studies taking place during a health emergency will be synthesized separately. These findings will be reviewed and discussed in the review team before being finalised.

Table 1. From CFIR (Damschroder et al., 2009) to analytical framework: constructs, exclusions, and operationalization for PIFU

Step in PIFU implementation	CFIR domain	CFIR constructs included	CFIR constructs excluded (rationale)	Operationalization — coder questions
The PIFU environment (RQ1: Factors affecting the PIFU approaches)	Intervention characteristics	Intervention source; Relative advantage; Adaptability; Complexity	Evidence strength & quality (addressed in effect review); Trialability (most studies concern PIFU already in use); Design quality & packaging (pertains to development, not experience); Cost (quantitative in nature; captured within Readiness)	Intervention source: Do stakeholders perceive PIFU as externally imposed or internally adopted? Advantage: What do stakeholders see as the relative advantage of PIFU (over scheduled follow-up)? Complexity: Is it easy to use, or does it clash with daily activities (at home, in the health services)? Adaptability: What adjustments have been made to fit stakeholders' needs (incl. subgroups)?
	Inner setting	Implementation climate (incl. tension for change, compatibility, relative priority, organisational incentives, goals & feedback, learning climate); Readiness for implementation (incl. leadership engagement, available resources, access to information & knowledge)	Structural characteristics; Networks & communications; Culture (relevant aspects absorbed into Implementation climate and Readiness sub-constructs)	Climate fit: Does PIFU fit with established ways and values of working/living, or does it create friction? Climate priority: Is PIFU seen and presented as a priority in a person's care? Readiness: Are the necessary infrastructure (IT, staff, funding) and resources (app, communication pathways) in place in the health services and at home to adopt PIFU? Are equitably available
	Outer setting	Patient needs & resources; Pressure to implement	Cosmopolitanism; External policy & incentives (too macro-level for a QES focused on stakeholder experience; partially captured via Pressure to implement)	Pressure: What external drivers (policy, peer organisations) are pushing PIFU use? Patient needs fit (HS): Do staff consider that patient needs and resources are accurately prioritized in the design of the PIFU approach?
The delivery (RQ2: health services staff's)	Characteristics of individuals	Knowledge & beliefs; Self-efficacy; Individual stage of change	Individual identification with organisation (too macro-level for a QES focused on a specific approach); Other personal attributes (too broad for the focus of this QES and	Knowledge and Beliefs (K&B_HS): What is staff attitude towards PIFU (note difference among staff)?

Step in PIFU implementation	CFIR domain	CFIR constructs included	CFIR constructs excluded (rationale)	Operationalization — coder questions
views, experiences and practices)			unlikely to be reported extensively in primary studies on stakeholders experience	<p>Self-efficacy: Do different staff groups feel capable of managing care under a PIFU approach?</p> <p>Stage of change: How experienced are different staff groups with PIFU as a routine practice?</p>
	Implementation process	Engaging; Executing	Planning; Reflecting & evaluating (less likely to be captured in qualitative accounts of stakeholder experience, which focus on enacted rather than planned or evaluated implementation)	<p>Engagement: Who is being engaged in PIFU delivery, and how?</p> <p>Executing in Practice: How is the service being executed in practice compared to the official PIFU protocol or intended use of the tools supporting PIFU (e.g. workaround, alternative use) ?</p>
The experience (RQ3: Patients & relatives)	Characteristics of individuals	Knowledge & beliefs; Self-efficacy; Individual stage of change	Same constructs as above, now applied to the patient and relative perspective)	<p>Knowledge and Beliefs (K&B_patient): What is the attitude of patients and their relatives towards the PIFU approach (e.g. trust, value, familiarity with PIFU)? Note differences among subgroups!</p> <p>Self-efficacy: Do they feel capable of managing their condition under PIFU?</p> <p>Stage of change: How experienced with PIFU as a routine practice are the people living with chronic conditions and/or their relatives? Note differences among subgroups!</p>
	Outer setting	Patient needs & resources	Re-applied here to capture fit between PIFU design and patients' home context and resources)	Context: Does the PIFU model fit the patient's home life, resources, and circumstances? Note differences among subgroups!
The consequence (RQ4: Shifts)	Cross-domain synthesis	Derived inductively from patterns across all stages	Not a standalone CFIR domain; emergent analytical layer based on insights about full implementation chain.	Coded inductively

Step in PIFU implementation	CFIR domain	CFIR constructs included	CFIR constructs excluded (rationale)	Operationalization — coder questions
Emergencies (RQ5)	Cross-domain synthesis	Constructs from all other domains + inductive codes if relevant	-	Coded as other studies, synthesised separately

Subgroup analyses

During the analysis, we will explore potential variations between different stakeholder populations facing inequities or at risk of facing inequities and in line with the guidance from the Campbell and Cochrane Equity Methods Group (Petkovic et al., 2025a, 2025b; Welch et al., 2024). We will analyse the data in each category or theme through the lens of selected population characteristics more specifically. Building on the subgroups identified in the effect review protocol (Bogale et al., 2026) and the PROGRESS+ framework (O’Neill et al., 2014), we identified important factors that may influence the views, experience and practice of PIFU services among stakeholders. Table 2 summarizes these factors and the rationale for their pre-selection.

To prioritise the most relevant factors of inequities, we will refine the list included in Table 2 using information derived from our consultation with stakeholders.

Table 2. Potential factors of inequities in stakeholders’ experience of PIFU

PROGRESS+ factor	Rational for inclusion
Place of Residence	Low- and middle-income countries carry the largest share of the global burden of chronic conditions(WHO, 2025b). However, existing literature on PIFU has come primarily from high-income countries (see Background). If relevant data is found, we will explore potential variations in the views, experiences and practices of stakeholders from HIC v. LMIC.
	Rural/Urban/slum Geographical disparities have been linked to higher risk of developing certain chronic conditions and poorer access to care, although the direction of this association may vary between conditions and countries. We expect that this factor will affect both the likelihood of offering/being offered PIFU (e.g. privileging people with better access to care in the first place) and stakeholder experience (e.g. benefits from fewer visits to healthcare providers, associated workload, different access to support and information).
Race, ethnicity, culture, language	In some countries, ethnic minorities, like any groups at risk of social disadvantage and discrimination, may carry a higher burden of chronic conditions (Lancet, 2023; WHO, 2025b). While these population groups may be over-represented among people with chronic conditions, they may also experience additional challenges using PIFU services due to e.g. language barrier, lack of knowledge of the health system, discrimination in access to care and treatment(Dretzke et al., 2023; Paterson et al., 2025). For example, in the UK, PIFU was both an issue of concerns and but also highly valued among people living with chronic conditions from ethnic minorities

	(Chainrai et al., 2024). Cultural and ethnic diversity among the professionals implementing PIFU may also influence the experience of people living with chronic conditions from minority groups (i.e. availability of professionals sharing the language and cultural background of patients from minority groups)(Dretzke et al., 2023).
Gender, sex	Gender is likely to shape several aspects and stakeholders of interest in this QES. First, gendered roles and professions may shape the experience and views of different stakeholders. For example, women are predominant among certain HCPs like nurses (WHO, 2026), who may be given new responsibilities under PIFU. Due to traditional care roles, women are also often involved in the care or support of a relative with a chronic condition, which may make their perspective particularly relevant to PIFU. Second, the PIFU experience of certain groups, like LGBTQ+ people, may be shaped by their experience of discrimination and poor access to healthcare. These challenges may also affect the likelihood of these groups being represented in primary studies.
Education	Risk of developing certain chronic conditions is correlated with lower level of education, which may affect the population likely to be eligible to or on PIFU in the first place (for example, Diabetes Type 2 (Bellou et al., 2018)). However, levels of education and health literacy are correlated (Kickbusch, 2001). Health literacy is an important component of PIFU acceptability and feasibility(Paterson et al., 2025). Therefore, we hypothesize that a patient’s level of education may affect their likelihood to be offered PIFU or stakeholders’ perception of their success under this approach.
Socioeconomic status	Poverty is linked with higher risk of chronic conditions and may be linked to poorer access to care and treatment (WHO, 2025b). This may affect both the representation of low-SES groups in studies’ population but also their experiences and views of the PIFU services. For example, low-SES groups may have face additional challenges accessing certain tools necessary to PIFU (e.g. digital technology, self-management devices) but may also experience greater benefits through the reduction of healthcare appointment. Variations in the perception of symptoms and health status among different SES groups have also been noted, which may affect patients’ likelihood to request a follow-up or HCPs likelihood to offer PIFU to certain population (Dretzke et al., 2023).
Social capital	Because of the chronic nature of our conditions of interest and their implications for people’s lifestyle, isolation or support networks play an important role in a person’s ability to manage their chronic condition (WHO, 2025a, 2025b).

	<p>As PIFU requires strong self-management, we hypothesize that a person’s support system (or lack thereof) may influence their likelihood of being offered PIFU or of successfully managing their conditions under the PIFU approach.</p>
<p>“+” factors: Age</p>	<p>We only focus on adults, due to the autonomy required to adopt PIFU.</p> <p>Chronic conditions are more prevalent among older age groups, which may affect their representation in primary studies on PIFU (WHO, 2025b). However, age has been identified as an important factor in the preferences of people living with chronic conditions and HCP decisions regarding PIFU (Chainrai et al., 2024; Dretzke et al., 2023). For example, certain characteristics of the PIFU intervention (e.g. digital elements) may be more challenging for older adults who are not used to using/implementing these tools (Chainrai et al., 2024). Therefore, we hypothesize that the view, experience and practice of people living with chronic conditions and their relatives as well as healthcare professionals may be different between age groups.</p>
<p>“+” factors: Type and duration of chronic condition</p>	<p>The demographics, risks and treatment requirements/needs differ according to the type of chronic condition. As a result, a PIFU approach may not be seen as equally suitable for all chronic conditions (Dretzke et al., 2023).</p> <p>We therefore hypothesize that the lived experience of PIFU may differ according to the condition (although the direction of this association is unknown at this point). We also hypothesize that the duration of the condition may also affect the experience of people living with chronic conditions and their relatives in particular, as it may affect their knowledge of their conditions as well as their experience with different approaches to chronic condition care. As the use of PIFU seems to vary across specialty (Reed & Crellin, 2022), we hypothesize that the views, experiences and practice of PIFU of HCP, health managers and support staff may vary according to specialties and the diseases they handle.</p>
<p>“+” factors: Disability and comorbidity</p>	<p>Due to the complications or disability some chronic conditions may lead to, some patients groups would have complex healthcare needs that involve managing several conditions or facing debilitating conditions that may affect their ability to access care. The suitability of PIFU for people with complex needs or with disability has been questions in previous studies (Chainrai et al., 2024; Dretzke et al., 2023)</p>

	As PIFU tends to be disease-specific, we hypothesize this approach may be more challenging for people living with multiple health conditions or with disabilities and the HCP managing their care.
--	--

Implications for practice

Once we have finished preparing the review findings, we will examine each finding, identify factors that could influence the implementation of the PIFU approach, and develop prompts for future implementers. These prompts will be presented in the implications for practice section. These prompts are not intended to be recommendations but will be phrased as questions to help implementers consider the implications of the review findings within their context. These prompts will be reviewed by a selection of stakeholders (see Stakeholder engagement).

Implications for health emergencies

Once we have finished preparing the review findings, we will examine each finding, identify factors that could influence the use or scale up of the PIFU approach in times of health emergencies, and develop prompts for health services managers and decision-makers. These prompts will be presented in a section on implications for health emergencies. These prompts are not intended to be recommendations but will be phrased as questions to help managers and decision-makers consider the implications of the review findings when confronted with a large, scaled emergency. These prompts will be reviewed by a selection of stakeholders from the RAPIDE project (see Stakeholder engagement).

Assessing our confidence in the review findings

Our review team will use the GRADE-CERQual (Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative research) approach collegially to assess our confidence in each finding (Lewin et al., 2018). GRADE-CERQual assesses confidence in the evidence, based on the following four key components.

1. Methodological limitations of included studies: the extent to which there are concerns about the design or conduct of the primary studies that contributed evidence to an individual review finding.
2. Coherence of the review finding: an assessment of how clear and cogent the fit is between the data from the primary studies and a review finding that synthesises those data. By cogent, we mean well supported or compelling.
3. Adequacy of the data contributing to a review finding: an overall determination of the degree of richness and quantity of data supporting a review finding.
4. Relevance of the included studies to the review question: the extent to which the body of evidence from the primary studies supporting a review finding is applicable to the context (perspective or population, phenomenon of interest, setting) specified

in the review question. In line with the TRANSFER approach (H. Munthe-Kaas et al., 2020), we will identify and prioritise factors related to the transferability of our findings during our initial consultation with stakeholders.

We will use the iSoQ software to support our confidence assessment and to make this assessment publicly available after publication.

After assessing each of the four components, we will make a judgement about the overall confidence in the evidence supporting the review finding. We will judge confidence as high, moderate, low, or very low. The final assessment will be based on consensus among the review authors. All findings start as high confidence and will then be graded down if there are important concerns regarding any of the GRADE-CERQual components.

Summary of Qualitative Findings table(s) and Evidence Profile(s)

We will present summaries of the findings and our assessments of confidence in these findings in the Summary of Qualitative Findings table(s). We will present detailed descriptions of our confidence assessment in an Evidence Profile(s).

Integrating the review findings with the effect review

As their scope differ slightly, the findings from the two reviews will be presented separately.

Review author reflexivity

All the reviewers were invited to answer a list of questions around reflexivity (see Appendix 2) as part of the writing of this protocol. An initial summary was prepared by one author (EB) and reviewed by all.

Our review team included health researchers with a variety of background, including social sciences, anthropology, nursing, public health and health systems. Several had expertise in thematics relevant to aspects of this QES: healthcare management, patient involvement, technology in health professional practice, health system research, service delivery research and implementation science. This diversity of background and areas of expertise manifested in our discussions around terminology and theoretical frameworks when developing the scope and subsequently, the protocol for this QES. Half of our team had primarily focused on the Norwegian health system in their research while the others have a global health background. Two members had practiced as healthcare providers in the past but had been working exclusively in health research for several years at the time of this QES. Only one of us has direct experience of a PIFU approach while another has researched PIFU approaches for a project.

Experience with QES varies strongly within our team, from members undertaking their first QES with this project to a senior methodologist having contributed to the development of several QES tools or methodological elements we plan to apply. Learning about different aspects of QES method or new tools has been identified by the team has a strong interest in this QES and is reflected in many of the choices presented in this protocol, including the

decisions to adopt newly developed tools if available (e.g. CAMELOT in iSoQ). However, all the reviewers have at least some experience with carrying out qualitative analysis.

Three reviewers indicated specific theories or approaches that may affect how they interpret data. These included a focus on implementation science theories, healthcare as social processes and interaction between stakeholders and technology in care; and a focus on health equity in health interventions. Another also highlighted the potential influence of previous QES experience in shaping their approach. When reflecting on their expectations for the results of the reviews, a common denominator was diversity, although the object of that diversity differs widely across reviewers (e.g. diversity of views, of settings, of implementation). Some reviewers also suspected that the intervention itself may, by design, be more common in, or more suitable to, certain settings (private sector, high-income settings) or specific patients. A common concern among some reviewers was the potential lack of qualitative studies on PIFU. Finally, some reviewers expressed their hope for a strong focus on the data and a strong empirical anchoring for the QES as well as producing findings that can be directly useful to decision-makers.

Acknowledgements

When preparing this protocol, we used the Cochrane Protocol and Review Template for Qualitative Evidence Synthesis (Glenton et al., 2023).

Contributions of authors

SL, MS, BB and EB defined the topic of the review and carried out initial scoping search to identify existing literature. The scope of the review, objective, research questions and inclusion/exclusion criteria were developed collegially by SL, BB, MS, EB, JDO and RK. The search strategy was developed by MCM.

EB drafted the protocol. All authors reviewed and provided feedback on the protocol.

Declarations of interest

The authors declare no financial conflicts of interest. SL led or was involved in the development of several methodological tools listed in this protocol (GRADE-CERQual, CAMELOT, TRANSFER) and associated software (iSoQ) but does not receive any financial compensation or incentives from the use of these tools.

References

Ames, H., Booth, A., & Noyes, J. (2024). Chapter 6: Selecting studies and sampling. In Jane

Noyes & Angela Harden (Eds), *Cochrane-Campbell Handbook for Qualitative Evidence*

Synthesis. Version 1. Cochrane. <https://training.cochrane.org/cochrane-campbell-handbook-qualitative-evidence-synthesis>

Balhorn, J., Su'a, B., Jin, J., Peng, S.-L., Weston, M., Israel, L., Connolly, A., Hill, A. G., & Taneja, A. (2022). Changing the routine: A move to patient initiated follow up to improve surgical outpatient clinic. *ANZ Journal of Surgery*, *92*(6), 1394–1400. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ans.17676>

Bellou, V., Belbasis, L., Tzoulaki, I., & Evangelou, E. (2018). Risk factors for type 2 diabetes mellitus: An exposure-wide umbrella review of meta-analyses. *PLOS ONE*, *13*(3), e0194127. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0194127>

Bogale, B., Solberg, M., Besnier, E., Marchant, M., Rachadell, J., Vareda, R., & Lewin, S. (2026). *Patient-initiated Follow-up in Diabetes care: A systematic review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.19206870>

Booth, A., & Carroll, C. (2015). How to build up the actionable knowledge base: The role of 'best fit' framework synthesis for studies of improvement in healthcare. *BMJ Quality & Safety*, *24*(11), 700–708. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs-2014-003642>

Brunton, G., Booth, A., & Carroll, C. (2024). Chapter 9. Framework Synthesis. In Jane Noyes & Angela Harden (Eds), *Cochrane-Campbell Handbook for Qualitative Evidence Synthesis. Version 1.* Cochrane. <https://training.cochrane.org/cochrane-campbell-handbook-qualitative-evidence-synthesis>

Canada's Drug Agency. (2026). *Qualitative Studies—MEDLINE* [Database]. Canada's Drug Agency. Canada's Drug Agency Search Filters Database. <https://searchfilters.cda-amc.ca/link/40>

Chainrai, M., Kershaw, V. F., Gray, T. G., & Radley, S. C. (2024). Patient-initiated follow-up in gynaecology: Patient and clinician views. *European Journal of Obstetrics &*

Gynecology and Reproductive Biology, 298, 18–22.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2024.04.032>

Critical Appraisal Skills Programme. (2022). *CASP Qualitative Studies Checklist [online]*. CASP.

<https://casp-uk.net/casp-tools-checklists/>

Damschroder, L. J., Aron, D. C., Keith, R. E., Kirsh, S. R., Alexander, J. A., & Lowery, J. C.

(2009). Fostering implementation of health services research findings into practice: A consolidated framework for advancing implementation science. *Implementation Science*, 4(1), 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-4-50>

Dretzke, J., Lorenc, A., Adriano, A., Herd, C., Mehanna, H., Nankivell, P., Moore, D. J., &

Team, the P. R. (2023). Systematic review of patients' and healthcare professionals' views on patient-initiated follow-up in treated cancer patients. *Cancer Medicine*, 12(15), 16531–16547. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cam4.6243>

Ester, M., White, K., Dhiman, K., Zafar, S., Subdar, S., Zimmermann, G. L., Hoens, A. M.,

Manske, S. L., Hazlewood, G., Lacaille, D., Barber, M. R. W., Panich, N., Jung, M.,

Perry, M. G., Twilt, M., Then, K. L., Charlton, A., & Barber, C. E. H. (2025a). A theory of change for patient-initiated follow-up care in rheumatoid arthritis. *BMC*

Rheumatology, 9(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41927-025-00481-3>

Ester, M., White, K., Dhiman, K., Zafar, S., Subdar, S., Zimmermann, G. L., Hoens, A. M.,

Manske, S. L., Hazlewood, G., Lacaille, D., Barber, M. R. W., Panich, N., Jung, M.,

Perry, M. G., Twilt, M., Then, K. L., Charlton, A., & Barber, C. E. H. (2025b). A theory of change for patient-initiated follow-up care in rheumatoid arthritis. *BMC*

Rheumatology, 9(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41927-025-00481-3>

Glenton, C., Bohren, M., Downe, S., Paulsen, E., & Lewin, S. (2023). *Cochrane Qualitative Evidence Syntheses: Protocol and review template v1.4*.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10050961>

- Glenton, C., Paulsen, E., Agarwal, S., Gopinathan, U., Johansen, M., Kyaddondo, D., Munabi-Babigumira, S., Nabukenya, J., Nakityo, I., Namaganda, R., Namitala, J., Neumark, T., Nsangi, A., Pakenham-Walsh, N. M., Rashidian, A., Royston, G., Sewankambo, N., Tamrat, T., & Lewin, S. (2024). Healthcare workers' informal uses of mobile phones and other mobile devices to support their work: A qualitative evidence synthesis. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (8).
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD015705.pub2>
- Hardy, S. (2024). The value of patient-initiated follow up: Insights from a highly specialised service. *British Journal of Health Care Management*, 30(7).
<https://doi.org/10.12968/bjhc.2023.0089>
- Horizon Europe RAPIDE project. (2026). *RAPIDE – Regular and Unplanned Care Adaptive Dashboard for Cross-Border Emergencies*. Horizon Europe. RAPIDE.
<https://www.rapideproject.eu/>
- Kershaw, V. F., Chainrai, M., & Radley, S. C. (2022). Patient initiated follow up in Obstetrics and Gynaecology: A systematic review. *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, 272, 123–129.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2022.02.181>
- Kickbusch, I. S. (2001). Health literacy: Addressing the health and education divide. *Health Promotion International*, 16(3), 289–297. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/16.3.289>
- Lancet, T. (2023). Diabetes: A defining disease of the 21st century. *The Lancet*, 401(10394), 2087. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(23\)01296-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(23)01296-5)
- Leitch, M., Arshad, A., Cohen, P. A., & Allanson, E. R. (2025). Patient-initiated follow-up in low-risk endometrial cancer after surgery: A systematic review. *International Journal of Gynecological Cancer*, 35(2), 100037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgc.2024.100037>

- Lewin, S., Booth, A., Glenton, C., Munthe-Kaas, H., Rashidian, A., Wainwright, M., Bohren, M. A., Tunçalp, Ö., Colvin, C. J., Garside, R., Carlsen, B., Langlois, E. V., & Noyes, J. (2018). Applying GRADE-CERQual to qualitative evidence synthesis findings: Introduction to the series. *Implementation Science*, *13*(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-017-0688-3>
- Munthe-Kaas, H. M., Booth, A., Sommer, I., Cooper, S., Garside, R., Hannes, K., Noyes, J., & Group, T. C. D. (2024). Developing CAMELOT for assessing methodological limitations of qualitative research for inclusion in qualitative evidence syntheses. *Cochrane Evidence Synthesis and Methods*, *2*(6), e12058. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cesm.12058>
- Munthe-Kaas, H., Nøkleby, H., Lewin, S., & Glenton, C. (2020). The TRANSFER Approach for assessing the transferability of systematic review findings. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, *20*(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-019-0834-5>
- O'Neill, J., Tabish, H., Welch, V., Petticrew, M., Pottie, K., Clarke, M., Evans, T., Pardo, J. P., Waters, E., White, H., & Tugwell, P. (2014). Applying an equity lens to interventions: Using PROGRESS ensures consideration of socially stratifying factors to illuminate inequities in health. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, *67*(1), 56–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2013.08.005>
- Page, M. J., Moher, D., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... McKenzie, J. E. (2021). PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: Updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, *372*, n160. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>

Pallath, A., & Zhang, Q. (2023). Paperfetcher: A tool to automate handsearching and citation searching for systematic reviews. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 14(2), 323–335.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1604>

Paterson, C., Chau, M., Turner, M. R., & Primeau, C. (2025). What is the Lived Experience of People Affected by Cancer, Family Members, and Their Treatment Team Engaged in Patient Initiated Follow-Up and Preferences in Cancer Care: A Qualitative Systematic Review. *Seminars in Oncology Nursing, Caring Life-Course Theory*, 41(6), 152041.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soncn.2025.152041>

Petkovic, J., Pardo, J. P., Welch, V., Dewidar, O., Maxwell, L. J., Darzi, A., Lotfi, T., Mbuagbaw, L., Pottie, K., & Tugwell, P. (2025a). Health Equity in Systematic Reviews: A Tutorial—Part 1 Getting Started With Health Equity in Your Review. *Cochrane Evidence Synthesis and Methods*, 3(6), e70055.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/cesm.70055>

Petkovic, J., Pardo, J. P., Welch, V., Dewidar, O., Maxwell, L. J., Darzi, A., Lotfi, T., Mbuagbaw, L., Pottie, K., & Tugwell, P. (2025b). Health Equity in Systematic Reviews: A Tutorial—Part 2 Implementing Health Equity Throughout Your Methods. *Cochrane Evidence Synthesis and Methods*, 3(6), e70054.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/cesm.70054>

Pollock, A., Morley, R., & Watts, C. (n.d.). *Involving people: A learning resource for systematic review authors*. Cochrane training. Retrieved 19 March 2026, from

<https://www.cochrane.org/learning->

[module/run/8018/index.htm?endpoint=https%3A//www.cochrane.org/learning-](https://www.cochrane.org/learning-module/run/8018/index.htm?endpoint=https%3A//www.cochrane.org/learning-)

[module/statements/8018/launchr/content/launch/468a2659-1070-4911-b7b3-](https://www.cochrane.org/learning-module/statements/8018/launchr/content/launch/468a2659-1070-4911-b7b3-)

[c2c073810694/xAPI&actor=%7B%22objectType%22%3A%22Agent%22%2C%22name%22%3A%22Elodie%20Besnier%22%2C%22account%22%3A%7B%22name%22%3A%22z1906141406306322231198244446170%22%2C%22homePage%22%3A%22https%3A%5C/%5C/account.cochrane.org%22%7D%7D](https://www.cochrane.org/learning-module/statements/8018/launchr/content/launch/468a2659-1070-4911-b7b3-c2c073810694/xAPI&actor=%7B%22objectType%22%3A%22Agent%22%2C%22name%22%3A%22Elodie%20Besnier%22%2C%22account%22%3A%7B%22name%22%3A%22z1906141406306322231198244446170%22%2C%22homePage%22%3A%22https%3A%5C/%5C/account.cochrane.org%22%7D%7D)

[3A%5C/%5C/account.cochrane.org%22%7D%7D](https://www.cochrane.org/learning-module/statements/8018/launchr/content/launch/468a2659-1070-4911-b7b3-c2c073810694/xAPI&actor=%7B%22objectType%22%3A%22Agent%22%2C%22name%22%3A%22Elodie%20Besnier%22%2C%22account%22%3A%7B%22name%22%3A%22z1906141406306322231198244446170%22%2C%22homePage%22%3A%22https%3A%5C/%5C/account.cochrane.org%22%7D%7D)

Reed, S., & Crellin, N. (2022). *Patient-initiated follow-up: Will it free up capacity in outpatient care?* (p. 32). NIHR RSET (Nuffield Trust and UCL).

<https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/research/patient-initiated-follow-up-will-it-free-up-capacity-in-outpatient-care>

Reed, S., & Nadia, C. (n.d.). *Patient-initiated follow-up: Will it free up capacity in outpatient care?* Nuffield Trust. Retrieved 27 January 2026, from

<https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/research/patient-initiated-follow-up-will-it-free-up-capacity-in-outpatient-care>

Sengupta, R., Bukhari, M., Cole, Z., Kyle, S., MacDonald, G., McKay, K., Irani, A., & Perry, M.

(2024). Patient Initiated Follow-Up (PIFU): How can rheumatology departments start to reap the benefits? A consensus document. *Rheumatology Advances in Practice*, 8(4), rkae091. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rap/rkae091>

Sherlaw-Johnson, C., Georghiou, T., Reed, S., Hutchings, R., Appleby, J., Bagri, S., Crellin, N.,

Kumpunen, S., Lobont, C., Negus, J., Ng, P. L., Oung, C., Spencer, J., & Ramsay, A.

(2024a). Evaluation of Patient-Initiated Follow-Up. In *Investigating innovations in outpatient services: A mixed-methods rapid evaluation*. National Institute for Health and Care Research. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK607633/>

Sherlaw-Johnson, C., Georghiou, T., Reed, S., Hutchings, R., Appleby, J., Bagri, S., Crellin, N.,

Kumpunen, S., Lobont, C., Negus, J., Ng, P. L., Oung, C., Spencer, J., & Ramsay, A.

(2024b). Investigating innovations in outpatient services: A mixed-methods rapid evaluation. *Health and Social Care Delivery Research*, 12(38), 1–162.

<https://doi.org/10.3310/VGQD4611>

Subdar, S., Dhiman, K., Hartfeld, N. M. S., Hoens, A. M., White, K., Manske, S. L., Hazlewood,

G., Lacaille, D., Lopatina, E., Barber, M. R. W., Mosher, D. P., Fifi-Mah, A., Twilt, M.,

Luca, N., Then, K. L., Crump, T., Zafar, S., Osinski, K., & Barber, C. E. H. (2024).

- Investigating the Influence of Patient Eligibility Characteristics on the Number of Deferrable Rheumatologist Visits: Planning for a Patient-Initiated Follow-Up Strategy. *Journal of Rheumatology*, 51(6), 587–595. <https://doi.org/10.3899/jrheum.2023-0891>
- Wagner, M., Rosumeck, S., Küffmeier, C., Döring, K., & Euler, U. (2020). A validation study revealed differences in design and performance of MEDLINE search filters for qualitative research. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 120, 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2019.12.008>
- Welch, V. A., Petkovic, J., Jull, J., Hartling, L., Klassen, T., Kristjansson, E., Pardo, J. P., Petticrew, M., Stott, D. J., Thomson, D., Ueffing, E., Williams, K., Young, C., & Tugwell, P. (2024). Equity and specific populations. In J. Higgins, J. Thomas, J. Chandler, M. Cumpston, T. Li, M. Page, V. Welch, & E. Flemyng (Eds), *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions version 6.5 [last updated October 2019]: Chapter 16* (Vols 1–26). Cochrane. [cochrane.org/handbook](https://www.cochrane.org/handbook)
- Whear, R., Thompson-Coon, J., Rogers, M., Abbott, R. A., Anderson, L., Ukoumunne, O., Matthews, J., Goodwin, V. A., Briscoe, S., Perry, M., & Stein, K. (2020). Patient-initiated appointment systems for adults with chronic conditions in secondary care. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD010763.pub2>
- WHO. (2025a, August 29). *Depressive disorder (depression)*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/depression>
- WHO. (2025b, September 25). *Noncommunicable diseases*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>
- WHO. (2026). *National Health Workforce Accounts Data Portal*. <https://apps.who.int/nhwaportal/>

World Health Organization. (2002). *Innovative Care for Chronic Conditions - Building Blocks*

for Action: Global Report. World Health Organization.

Sources of support

External sources

Funded by the European Union – RAPIDE project (Grant No. 101136348). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix 1. Pilot search in EMBASE

Search Strategy PIFU and Chronic Conditions

Data base: EMBASE (via Elsevier)

Sources: EMBASE, Not-Medline, Preprints

Date: 1995-Mars 2026

Filter for Qualitative Research. Adaptation for EMBASE Elsevier from:

Translated from our MEDLINE filter, internally validated using gold standard database set from: Wagner M, Rosumeck S, Küffmeier C, Döring K, Euler U. A validation study revealed differences in design and performance of MEDLINE search filters for qualitative research. [J Clin Epidemiol. 2020 Apr; 120:17-24.](#)

Search Query	Results
1 ((patient* NEAR/2 initiated):ti,ab) OR pifu:ti,ab	22,349
2 (patient* NEAR/1 led):ti,ab	4,378
3 ((patient* OR self) NEAR/2 ('open access*' OR 'direct access*' OR 'advanced access*' OR 'center* access*')):ti,ab	556
4 'self referr*':ti,ab	5,047
5 'self request*':ti,ab	43
6 ((patient* OR self) NEAR/2 'help seek*'):ti,ab	533
7 ((patient* OR self) NEAR/2 'shared care'):ti,ab	220
8 ((patient* OR self) NEAR/1 (choice* OR choos* OR flexib*)):ti,ab	11,220
9 ((patient* OR self) NEAR/2 (unscheduled* OR 'out of hours' OR 'same day schedule*' OR 'demand based')):ti,ab	589
10 ((patient* OR self) NEAR/2 (mail* OR phone* OR telephone* OR messag*)):ti,ab	12,200
11 #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10	56,517
12 consultation*:ti,ab OR appointment*:ti,ab OR visit*:ti,ab OR clinic*:ti,ab	9,853,923
13 checkup*:ti,ab OR 'check up*':ti,ab OR 'check-up*':ti,ab	35,709

Search Query	Results
14 'follow up'/exp OR followup*:ti,ab OR 'follow-up*':ti,ab	3,243,795
15 #12 OR #13 OR #14	11,600,573
16 #11 AND #15	37,556
17 ('patient* schedule*' NEAR/2 (appointment* OR visit* OR 'follow up')):ti,ab	161
18 ('same day' NEAR/2 (appointment* OR visit* OR schedule*)):ti,ab	611
19 ('open access' NEAR/2 (appointment* OR visit* OR schedule*)):ti,ab	45
20 (patient* NEAR/3 access* NEAR/3 ('follow up*' OR visit* OR appointment* OR consultation)):ti,ab	554
21 ('patient initiated' NEAR/4 ('follow up*' OR appointment* OR consultation* OR contact*)):ti,ab	397
22 #17 OR #18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21	1,751
23 #16 OR #22	38,855
24 'empirical research'/exp OR 'empirical research':ti,ab,kw	16,656
25 interview:it OR 'interview'/exp OR 'interviews as topic':ti,ab,kw	488,137
26 'personal narrative'/it OR 'personal narrative':ti,ab,kw OR 'personal narratives as topic':ti,ab,kw	527
27 'focus group'/exp OR 'focus group' OR 'focus group*':ti,ab,kw	105,261
28 'narrative'/exp OR 'narrative' OR narration:ti,ab OR narrative*:ti,ab	139,492
29 'nursing methodology research':ti,ab,kw	65
30 interview*:ti,ab OR questionnaire*:ti,ab,kw	1,797,735
31 theme:ti,ab OR thematic:ti,ab OR qualitative:ti,ab,kw	610,886
32 'ethnological research':ti,ab,kw OR ethnograph*:ti,ab,kw OR ethnosing:ti,ab,kw	18,628
33 phenomenol*:ti,ab,kw OR 'grounded theor*':ti,ab,kw OR 'grounded stud*':ti,ab,kw OR 'grounded research':ti,ab,kw OR 'grounded analys*':ti,ab,kw	70,184
34 'life stor*':ti,ab,kw OR 'women s stor*':ti,ab,kw OR emic:ti,ab,kw OR etic:ti,ab,kw	3,976
35 hermeneutic*:ti,ab,kw OR heuristic*:ti,ab,kw OR semiotic:ti,ab,kw OR 'data saturat*':ti,ab OR 'participant observ*':ti,ab	37,810

Search Query	Results
36 'social construct*':ti,ab OR postmodern*':ti,ab OR 'post-structural*':ti,ab OR 'post structural*':ti,ab OR poststructural*':ti,ab OR 'post modern*':ti,ab OR 'post-modern*':ti,ab	5,778
37 feminis*':ti,ab OR 'action research':ti,ab OR 'cooperative inquir*':ti,ab OR 'co-operative inquir*':ti,ab OR humanistic:ti,ab OR existential:ti,ab OR experiential:ti,ab OR paradigm*':ti,ab	315,492
38 'field stud*':ti,ab OR 'field research':ti,ab OR 'human science':ti,ab OR 'biographical method*':ti,ab OR 'theoretical sampl*':ti,ab,kw OR 'purposeful sampl*':ti,ab OR 'purposive sampl*':ti,ab	56,379
39 account:ti,ab OR accounts:ti,ab OR unstructured:ti,ab OR 'open-ended':ti,ab OR texts:ti,ab OR textual:ti,ab OR 'life world':ti,ab OR 'life-world':ti,ab	832,427
40 'conversation analys*':ti,ab OR 'personal experience*':ti,ab OR 'theoretical saturation':ti,ab OR 'lived experience*':ti,ab OR 'life experience*':ti,ab	64,887
41 'cluster sampl*':ti,ab OR 'observational method*':ti,ab OR 'content analysis':ti,ab OR 'constant comparative':ti,ab OR 'constant comparison':ti,ab OR 'discourse analys*':ti,ab OR 'discursive analys*':ti,ab OR 'narrative analys*':ti,ab	94,943
42 heidegger*':ti,ab OR colaizzi*':ti,ab OR spiegelberg*':ti,ab OR 'van manen*':ti,ab OR 'van kaam*':ti,ab OR 'merleau ponty*':ti,ab OR husserl*':ti,ab OR foucault:ti,ab OR ricoeur:ti,ab OR glaser*':ti,ab OR (corbin*':ti,ab AND strauss*':ti,ab)	8,046
43 #24 OR #25 OR #26 OR #27 OR #28 OR #29 OR #30 OR #31 OR #32 OR #33 OR #34 OR #35 OR #36 OR #37 OR #38 OR #39 OR #40 OR #41 OR #42	3,517,249
44 #23 AND #43	10,358
45 #23 AND #43 AND [1995-2026]/py	10,217
46 adult*':ti,ab,kw OR [adult]/lim OR [young adult]/lim OR [middle aged]/lim OR [aged]/lim OR [very elderly]/lim	14,468,387

47	#45 AND #46	7,087
48	#45 AND #46 AND ('article'/it OR 'article in press'/it OR 'conference abstract'/it OR 'conference paper'/it OR 'conference review'/it OR 'data papers'/it OR 'review'/it OR 'preprint'/it)	6,263
49	#45 AND #46 AND ('article'/it OR 'article in press'/it OR 'conference abstract'/it OR 'conference paper'/it OR 'conference review'/it OR 'data papers'/it OR 'review'/it OR 'preprint'/it) AND ([embase]/lim OR [preprint]/lim)	5,562

Appendix 2. Reflexivity questions

Based on Francisco M. Olmos-Vega, Renée E. Stalmeijer, Lara Varpio & Renate Kahlke (2023)
A practical guide to reflexivity in qualitative research: AMEE Guide No. 149, Medical Teacher,
45:3, 241-251, DOI: 10.1080/0142159X.2022.2057287

- What is your background? How do you think your experience may shape your role in the project?
- What is your experience with QES?
- What approaches or theories do you tend to favor in QES?
- Do you have any experience with PIFU interventions?
- What do you expect the review to find? (“No idea” is an acceptable answer!)
- What would you like the review to find? (“No opinion” is an acceptable answer!)